

Research Article

INCIDENCE OF CARDIOVASCULAR RISK FACTORS AMONG LEISURE TIME PHYSICAL ACTIVITY PARTICIPANTS

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Abstract

Background: Physical exercise is widely promoted for cardiovascular health, yet some active individuals still present with cardiovascular risk factors. This study investigated the incidence of cardiovascular risk factors among adults engaging in Leisure Time Physical Activity (LTPA) in Delta State, Nigeria, and explored associations with demographic, lifestyle, and activity patterns.

Methodology: A cross-sectional descriptive survey was conducted among 300 adults aged range of 30-60years. The subjects were recruited from fitness center and sports clubs using multi-stage sampling techniques. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire, anthropometric, blood pressure measurements and blood samples were collected for biochemical analyses (fasting blood glucose and lipid profile). Descriptive and inferential statistics, including t-tests, ANOVA, correlations, and regression analysis were performed using SPSS at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Obesity prevalence was high (68.0%), and 63.3% had central obesity. Hypertension affected 42.3% (SBP ≥ 140 mmHg) and 38.7% (DBP ≥ 90 mmHg). Abnormal fasting glucose was recorded in 34.0% (22.7% pre-diabetic, 11.3% diabetic). Borderline-to-high cholesterol levels were common (40.9%), with 36.7% elevated LDL-C. Higher LTPA frequency was inversely associated with BMI ($\beta = -2.76$, $p < 0.001$) and improved lipid profiles ($p < 0.05$), though BP associations were modest. Logistic regression showed low LTPA increased hypertension odds 2.45-fold ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: LTPA should be promoted as part of a broader, integrated lifestyle modification approach to maximize cardiovascular risk reduction.

Recommendation: Further longitudinal and mechanistic studies are warranted to better understand the optimal dosage and interaction of LTPA with other risk factors to enhance prevention strategies.

Key words: Incidence, Physical Activity, Cardiovascular, Risk Factor, Leisure Time Physical Activity

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain the leading cause of death globally, claiming an estimated 20 million lives annually and affecting over half a billion individuals [1]. These conditions, which encompass coronary artery disease, stroke, hypertensive heart disease, and other vascular disorders, impose a profound public health and socioeconomic burden. Global epidemiological data from the Global Burden of Cardiovascular Diseases Collaboration indicate that the majority of these deaths are preventable, as they arise from modifiable risk factors such as physical inactivity, poor diet, tobacco use, and obesity [2]. Physical inactivity has been identified as being a major lifestyle shift that is responsible for the onset and increased prevalence of these diseases [1]. The World Health Organization reports;

that the prevalence of cardiovascular diseases has assumed an alarming rate in recent years. By 2005, the total number of deaths arising from cardiovascular disease had increased globally to 17.5 million. Coronary heart disease alone was responsible for 7.6 million of these deaths and 5.7 million was due to stroke [15]. Various studies have estimated the impact of insufficient physical activity on the prevalence of diseases and estimated a very high direct medical cost to physical inactivity [1, 3]. In an earlier study [4], compared physical activity with all-cause mortality in 16,936 subjects. Death rate declined steadily after 16 years follow-up as the energy expenditure increased. A consequent prospective finding on the same subjects showed a graded inverse relationship between total physical activity and all-cause mortality [5]. In a similar approach, the level of individual

fitness and mortality rate was compared over an 8-year period [6]. Results of the study show that the age adjusted mortality rate declined across fitness quintile. In a subsequent study, the association involving risk of mortality and changes in physical fitness level was assessed in men [7]. The men were made to undergo two clinical examinations to ascertain changes in physical fitness associated with risk of death during the follow-up period. The highest age-adjusted all-cause mortality rate was present in the men who had a poor physical fitness at both clinical examinations whereas the lowest rate of mortality was observed in those men who had a good physical fitness level at both examinations [8], concluded in their study of physical activity and all-cause mortality in women that “by adhering to physical activity guidelines and expending about 1,000 kcal of energy per week, women can postpone mortality”.

[9], reported that about 15% of recently diagnosed cardiovascular diseases are attributable to a sedentary lifestyle. Thus, lifestyle modification has become a cornerstone of both primary and secondary prevention strategies, and among these modifiable behaviours, physical activity particularly leisure-time physical activity has emerged as a potent determinant of cardiovascular health [1].

There is currently an increased global interest in physical activities that promote health. Clinical researchers have articulated a burgeoning interest in the investigation of the incidence and degree of specific alterations in the physiological parameters of various systems of the human body following the application of physical exercise [1,10]. The physiological responses and adaptations to various intensities of physical exercise is now acknowledged as an essential instrument which can aid the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases and now widely accepted as a means for the primary prevention of cardiovascular diseases and effective treatment and rehabilitation regimen in patients [11, 12].

Leisure-time physical activity (LTPA) refers to voluntary movement performed during free time, undertaken with the purpose of recreation, health improvement, or fitness. It includes activities such as brisk walking, swimming, cycling, sports participation, and structured exercise programs. Unlike occupational physical activity, which is dictated by job demands and often characterized by repetitive low-intensity work with limited cardiovascular benefit, LTPA is generally self-paced, adaptable, and performed under conditions that allow for adequate recovery, making it physiologically more favourable [13, 14].

There are numerous risk factors linked with cardiovascular diseases broadly classified into modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. Non-modifiable risk factors are predisposing conditions that cannot be changed such as age, whereas modifiable risk factors include those conditions that can be changed by embracing a change in lifestyle. The Canadian Heart and Stroke Foundation identified nine major modifiable risk factors for chronic diseases to include sedentary lifestyle, tobacco smoking, alcohol abuse, poor nutrition, obesity, hypertension, high concentrations of dietary fat and blood lipids, and high blood glucose concentrations [16]. In a case controlled study [17], studied the association between potential risk factors and acute myocardial infarction from 52 countries across various continents. In conclusion of the study, two major significant risk factors for myocardial infarction are cigarette smoking and an abnormal ratio of blood lipids. Other accompanying seven risk factors were identified which include type 2 diabetes, high blood pressure, abdominal obesity and psychosocial factors, poor nutritional habits, alcohol consumption and physical inactivity. The author's conclusion is that these nine risk factors collectively predict 90% of the risk of a heart attack in men and 94% in women globally, irrespective of the geographical location, ethnic group, sex or age. Through regular physical activity, healthy diet and smoking cessation, it is likely to greatly reduce chronic diseases risk irrespective of gender and age. According to O'Donnell et al., [18], the modifiable risk factors are

codependent, and changing one risk factor may influence the degree of other risk factors.

The 2018 Physical Activity Guidelines Advisory Committee stated that the knowledge to prevent and control chronic diseases now exists [19]. In their report, a clear affirmation was made showing that regular participation in physical exercise remains the best choice for public health. In addition, the report stated that regular participation in physical exercise plays a prominent role in disease prevention, promote healthier sleep, enhances a sense of wellbeing, and improve performance of activities of daily living. The recommended target range is 500 to 1,000 metabolic equivalent/minutes (MET/min.) of moderate to vigorous dynamic physical exercise which is comparable to 150 to 300 minutes of dynamic physical exercise of moderate intensity on a weekly basis. The 1995 recommended guidelines which were reviewed in 2008 indicated that at least 30 minutes of physical exercise of moderate intensity on most or all days of the week would be appropriate and result in significant health benefits [20]. Thus, all healthy adults need moderate intensity aerobic physical activity for at least 30 minutes at five days on weekly basis or dynamic exercise of high intensity physical activity for at least 20 minutes on three days per week. Moderate intensity is equated to burning 3.5- 7.0 kcal/minute such as walking on level terrain at 3.0-4.5 mph or riding a bicycle at 5.0-9.0 mph. Vigorous intensity is categorized as burning 7.0 or more kcal/ minute such as running at above 5.0 mph riding a bicycle at above 10.0 mph.

From a public health perspective, promoting leisure-time physical activity remains an essential strategy to curb the global cardiovascular epidemic. The World Health Organization and the US Preventive Services Task Force recommend that adults engage in at least 150 minutes of moderate-intensity or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity activity per week for substantial health benefits, with additional gains achieved by doubling these amounts [21]. In 1995, the American College of Sports Medicine and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention gave the first contemporary recognition of the recommendation for moderate to vigorous physical activity to be adopted in order to achieve a health and fitness benefits [20]. This recommendation was summarized and stated that intermittent bouts of physical exercise, totaling 30 minutes or more on most days provided beneficial health and fitness effects. This resulted in a new paradigm, and the 2008 Guidelines continued to support this recommendation for adults, stating that “dynamic physical exercise ought to be performed in episodes of 10 minutes”. The report further suggested that related health support strategies can be applied globally for the prevention of premature death and disability associated with chronic diseases.

An individual need to walk at least 3,000 steps in 30 minutes on five days per week in order to meet current guidelines, [22]. In a prospective study [23], studied 416,175 subjects between 1996 and 2008. Their results revealed that those who exercised for 15 minutes per day had a 14% risk reduction of mortality and an increased life expectancy of 3years in contrast with the inactive group. It was further reported that for every additional daily exercise for 15 minutes, additional reduction by 4% in mortality and by 1% of cancer mortality was incurred. Nine manuscripts reviewed by the 2018 Physical Activity Guidelines Advisory Committee [19] show that; four out of the nine manuscripts, used a cross-sectional design, while four used a prospective design and one used a randomized controlled design. The subjects in the nine reviewed studies were middle-age and above, multiple races and ethnicities, males and females, a continuum of body sizes, and different geographical locations were represented so as to support the generalization of the conclusions. The studies reported incidences in health benefits that are related to metabolic syndrome, diabetes mellitus, and a composite of cardiovascular disorders. The daily number of steps varied across the studies but there was an approximately median step of 5,000 per day. Light intensity physical exercise characterized most of the steps, according to one of the reports stating that about 80% of the steps

were of light intensity. On age related disparity, younger or middle aged adults had more daily steps than older adults, [24], provided evidence that increasing steps per day reduces cardiovascular event and that the baseline step count have effect on subsequent cardiovascular disease events. In their study, more than 45,000 people participated including years of follow up in which 531 cardiovascular events occurred. A positive correlation existed between increase in daily steps and baseline steps resulting in a reduced risk for cardiovascular disease events.

[25] studied risk associated with type 2 diabetes. The study involved 3 days weekly supervised walk for duration of 3 months comprising of 78 subjects whose glucose profile was abnormal. They reported no improvement with the levels of the glucose profiles. Navigator data was analyzed by [26]. They found a progressive decline in the 6year metabolic syndrome score with baseline step count [27], reported that a negative association between previous daily steps and 2 hour levels of glucose after alteration for levels of glucose in the preceding 3 years. Ponsonby et al., [28] studied 458 adults with a normal glucose profile for 5years and establish that higher daily steps at baseline were correlated with a reduced incidence risk for impaired glucose tolerance. On the relationship with gait speed [29], analyzed 9 cohort studies involving 34,485 elderly adults with baseline gait speed and monitored between 6years to 21years found that the speed of gait was associated with survival in older adults.

To evaluate the dose-response relationship between physical activity, various chronic diseases, and all-cause mortality [30], studied the parameters of physical activity dose, volume intensity, duration, and frequency in 44 published articles. Their research showed that an inverse relationship exists between volume of physical activity and mortality rates regardless of age and that compliance to the recent minimum guidelines of physical exercise is associated with a 20-30% reduction in all-cause mortality [27], reported that a yearly daily increase of 2,000 resulted in an 8 percent yearly reduction in cardiovascular event rate in patients with impaired glucose tolerance. Furthermore, it was reported that for every 2,000 step additional daily steps, a 0.29 percent decrease in the 6 year score in metabolic syndrome was observed [26].

However, surveillance of cardiovascular health parameters in physically active populations is equally critical, as incident risk factors may otherwise remain undetected until they contribute to overt disease. The scientific gap lies in the limited number of studies focusing specifically on the incidence of cardiovascular risk factors within leisure-time physically active cohorts. Most investigations either compare active versus sedentary populations or examine general cardiovascular disease outcomes without isolating the active subset. Moreover, variability in how LTPA is quantified whether by self-report questionnaires prone to recall bias or by device-based accelerometry complicates the interpretation of findings and the ability to draw precise conclusions [31]. Understanding why some active individuals remain protected while others develop risk factors could lead to refined recommendations on the type, intensity, and volume of activity best suited for particular risk profiles, as well as highlight the need for integrated interventions addressing diet, stress management, and other determinants. This study investigated the incidence of cardiovascular risk factors among adults engaging in Leisure Time Physical Activity (LTPA) in Delta State, Nigeria, and explored associations with demographic, lifestyle, and activity patterns.

Materials and Method

Research Design: This study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive survey design. The cross-sectional approach is suitable for determining the prevalence or incidence of health-related states or events in a defined population at a specific point in time [32]. A descriptive survey design allows for the collection of both subjective (self-reported) and objective (measured) data, making it ideal for investigating lifestyle patterns, physical activity

behavior, and physiological risk factors. Although cross-sectional designs do not establish causality, they are well-suited for hypothesis generation and for identifying associations between leisure-time physical activity and cardiovascular risk profiles [33]. Additionally, they provide an efficient and cost-effective means of collecting data from a relatively large number of participants within a defined period.

Study Area: The research was conducted in selected fitness and sports clubs in Asaba metropolis, Delta state. These settings are ideal for targeting LTPA participants, as they represent environments where individuals voluntarily engage in physical activity for fitness, leisure, or health reasons. Multiple centers were selected across the metropolis to reflect urban, peri-urban, and rural areas to improve geographic and socio-demographic representation.

Target Population: The target population consists of adult leisure-time physical activity participants, defined as individuals aged 30 years and above who engage in structured or unstructured physical activity during their free time for at least one hour per day, 3 times a week over the past one year.

The inclusion criteria are

- Adults aged 30 to 60 years
- Individuals who voluntarily engage in LTPA
- Individuals who consent to participate in the study
- Residents of the selected area and participated actively in LTPA for over one year

Exclusion criteria are

- Individuals with pre-existing diagnosed cardiovascular diseases
- Those engaging only in occupational or transport-related physical activity
- Individuals on medications that could significantly alter lipid profiles or blood pressure.

Sample Size Determination: The sample size for this study was calculated using Cochran's formula for cross-sectional studies [34]:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot P \cdot (1 - P)}{e^2}$$

Where:

- n = required sample size
- Z = standard normal deviate at 95% confidence level (1.96)
- p = estimated proportion of the population with cardiovascular risk factors (assumed to be 0.5 for maximum variability)
- e = margin of error (set at 5%, i.e., 0.05)

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = 284.16$$

Thus, a minimum of 285 participants were required. Considering a potential 10% non-response rate, the adjusted sample size was:

$$285 + (0.10 \times 285) = 300$$

Therefore, a total sample size of 300 participants was engaged.

Sampling Technique: A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to ensure representativeness:

Stage 1 – Site Selection: Fitness centers and sports clubs was purposively selected based on accessibility and participation volume.

Stage 2 – Stratification: Sites were stratified based on geographic region (urban vs rural) or type of facility (private gym vs public sports center).

Stage 3 – Systematic Random Sampling: Within each site, participants were selected using systematic random sampling.

Data Collection and Instruments

Data was collected using the following instruments:

Structured Questionnaire: A structured, self-administered questionnaire was used to collect information on:

- Socio-demographic data (age, sex, education, occupation, income)
- Physical activity habits (frequency, duration, type, and intensity of LTPA)

- Lifestyle behaviors (smoking, alcohol consumption, dietary habits)
- Medical history and family history of cardiovascular diseases Knowledge and awareness of cardiovascular risk factors.

The questionnaire was adapted from the WHO STEP wise Approach to Surveillance (STEPS) tool [35] and the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) [36].

Anthropometric Measurements: Standardized procedures was followed to assess:

Weight (kg) using a calibrated digital scale and Height (m) using a stadiometer

Waist circumference (cm) measured at the midpoint between the lower rib and iliac crest

From these, Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated using:

$$BMI = \frac{Weight (kg)}{(Height (m))^2}$$

BMI classifications follow WHO standards (37):

Underweight: < 18.5 kg/m²

Normal: 18.5–24.9 kg/m²

Overweight: 25.0–29.9 kg/m²

Obese: ≥ 30.0 kg/m²

Height

This was measured using Stadiometer (Ayron 226, USA); which is a measuring scale for height calibrated in centimeters. The participants each was instructed to stand barefooted on the platform of the height scale with feet together. The knees were flexed at 180° while the participants rested against the height scale with the back with the eyes looking forward. The measure of the height was taken as the space from the scale platform to the vertex of the head which was read and recorded.

Weight

The participants were weighed using the weighing scale. Measurement was done using Digital Weighing Scale (BEU-GS27–007, Beurer GmbH; Ulm, Germany). Digital Weighing Scale (DWSs) has excellent reliability in static limb loading measurement [38]. Each participant was instructed to wear light clothing then stand barefooted, one foot on each side of the scale still standing straightforward on the weighing scale with the arms were kept by the side.

Blood pressure Assessment

All blood pressure measurements were taken according to the 2019 American College of Cardiology (ACC)/ American Heart Association (AHA) [39] guideline for blood pressure measurement [40], which require subjects to rest in a quiet environment for at least 10 minutes prior to the measurement. The subjects were made to rest in a comfortably seated position for at least 15minutes, with the back supported, legs uncrossed. The position adopted by the subjects during measurement was upright position in a chair with the arms supported on a table. The cuff was placed around the participant's left arm over the left brachial artery, about 1.5cm directly above the antecubital fossa and levelled with the heart. Measuring instruction required that the subjects remained silent throughout the procedure. The position adopted by the subjects during measurement was upright position in a chair while the upper limbs were supported on the table, lower limbs uncrossed and feet were positioned flat on the floor. The lowest of three measures was used for analysis, as reported by [41], since it has been previously stated that initial measurements are often higher than subsequent measures, and so are not reflective of true resting arterial pressures [42]. Each of the three measures were separated by an interval of 60 seconds, which is in agreement by way of earlier recommendations and studies [43, 41].

Electronic Sphygmomanometer

Resting Blood Pressure and Pulse Rate measurements were made using an automated monitor (Dinamap Pro 300, GEMedical Systems, Berks, UK). The Dinamap Pro 300 device was evaluated for accurateness and dependability of measurement by means of the mercury sphygmomanometer.

Blood Sample Collection

Five milliliters of intravenous blood samples was collected after overnight fasting (10–12 hr). Following about 10minutes of a seated rest in a chair, venous blood was sampled from the antecubital vein into a vacutainer tube. Immediately following collection, blood samples were allowed to settle at room temperature for 20 minutes to 1 hour in the vacutainer tubes using standard aseptic techniques to be clotted, and formerly centrifuged for 20 min to isolate serum from plasma. Blood Samples was then tested in collaboration with partner laboratory for the assessment of Lipid Profile, including Total Cholesterol, HDL, LDL, and Triglycerides.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments: Validity refers to the accuracy of the instrument in measuring what it is supposed to measure. The questionnaire was content validated by a panel of experts in public health, exercise physiology, and epidemiology. Reliability was tested using a pilot study involving 30 participants (excluded from the final sample). Equipment will be regularly calibrated to ensure measurement accuracy.

Procedure for Data Collection: The research team, comprising of trained assistants, visited selected centres on peak activity days. A group discussion was done and each participant:

1. Was briefed about the purpose of the study and sign a consent form.
2. Completed the questionnaire under supervision.
3. Undergo anthropometric and blood pressure measurements.
4. Provide fasting blood samples for glucose and lipid analysis.

All data was recorded anonymously using unique participant codes to maintain confidentiality.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Review Board of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta state, Nigeria (RBC/FBMC/DELSU/25/749).

Informed Consent: written informed consent was obtained from Participants

Confidentiality: Data was stored securely and only accessed by the research team.

Voluntariness: Participation was voluntary, with the right to withdraw at any time.

Beneficence: Participants with abnormal findings were advised to seek medical consultation.

Method of Data Analysis: Data was coded and analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used as follows:

Descriptive Statistics

Frequency distributions and percentages (for categorical variables)

Means and standard deviations (for continuous variables)

Inferential Statistics

Chi-square tests: To examine associations between categorical variables (e.g., smoking status and gender).

T-tests / ANOVA: To compare mean differences in risk factors across activity levels or age groups.

Binary logistic regression: To identify predictors of cardiovascular risk (e.g., odds of hypertension in smokers vs non-smokers).

Pearson or Spearman correlation: To assess relationships between continuous variables (e.g., waist circumference and systolic BP). A p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Demographic Data of Respondents:

The analysis of the demographic data of the 300 respondents that participated in the study. The diverse profile captured in these demographic data contributes to a comprehensive understanding of cardiovascular risk factors among leisure time physical activity.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Demographic Data of the Participant (n= 300)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	174	58.0%
	Female	126	42.0%
Age Group (Years)	30–39	45	15.0%
	40–49	136	45.3%
	50–59	89	29.7%
	60+	30	10.0%

Statistical Interpretation: Table 1: The sample comprised more males (58.0%) than females (42.0%), indicating a male predominance among leisure-time physical activity participants. The largest age group was 40–49 years (45.3%), followed by 50–59 years (29.7%), while participants aged 30–39 years (15.0%) and 60 years and above (10.0%) were less represented. This suggests that middle-aged adults formed the majority of respondents in the study.

Figure 1: Demographic Data of the Participant (Age and Gender)

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Demographics of BMI (n= 300)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
BMI Classification	Underweight (<18.5)	3	1.0%
	Normal (18.5–24.9)	25	8.3%
	Overweight (25–29.9)	68	22.7%
	Obese (≥30)	204	68.0%
Central Obesity	High Risk Waist Circumference	190	63.3%
Height (cm)	150–159	4	1.3%
	160–169	62	21.1%

	170–179	178	60.5%
	180–189	38	12.9%
	≥190	12	4.1%

Statistical Interpretation: The table indicates that most participants were obese (68.0%), followed by overweight individuals (22.7%), with only 8.3% having a normal BMI and 1.0% being underweight. Central obesity, defined by a high-risk waist circumference, was observed in 63.3% of respondents.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Demographic of Lifestyle Factor (n= 300)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Smoking Status	Yes	135	45.0%
	No	165	55.0%
Drinking Status	Yes	180	60.0%
	No	120	40.0%
Family History of CVD	Yes	127	42.3%
	No	173	57.7%

Statistical Interpretation: The table shows that 45.0% of respondents reported smoking, while 60.0% consumed alcohol. Additionally, 42.3% had a family history of cardiovascular disease, indicating that a significant proportion of participants possessed both behavioural and hereditary risk factors for cardiovascular health.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Blood Pressure Pulse Rate and Fasting Blood Glucose Profile of Respondents

Parameter	Category / Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Blood Pressure	Systolic ≥140 mmHg	127	42.3%
	Diastolic ≥90 mmHg	116	38.7%
Pulse Rate	60–100 bpm	282	94.0%
	101–130 bpm	18	6.0%
Fasting Blood Glucose (mmol/L)	4.0–5.5 (Normal)	198	66.0%
	5.6–6.9 (Pre-diabetes)	68	22.7%
	≥7.0 (Diabetes)	34	11.3%

Statistical Interpretation: Table 4: The table shows that elevated blood pressure was common, with 42.3% having systolic values ≥140 mmHg and 38.7% having diastolic values ≥90 mmHg. Most participants (94.0%) had a normal pulse rate of 60–100 bpm, while 6.0% recorded higher values. Regarding fasting blood glucose, 66.0% were within the normal range, 22.7% were pre-diabetic, and 11.3% were diabetic, indicating notable prevalence of abnormal glucose levels in the group.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Lipid Profile of Respondents (n=300)

Parameter	Category / Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	3.3–3.5	32	10.7%
	3.6–3.9	56	18.7%
	4.0–4.5	89	29.7%
	4.6–5.0	70	23.3%
	5.1–5.3	53	17.6%

Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0.1–0.4	29	9.7%
	0.5–0.8	60	20.0%
	0.9–1.2	76	25.3%
	1.3–1.5	74	24.7%
	1.6–1.7	61	20.3%

Statistical Interpretation: Table 5: Total cholesterol levels were most frequently observed in the 4.0–4.5 mmol/L range (29.7%), with notable proportions also in the 4.6–5.0 mmol/L (23.3%) and 5.1–5.3 mmol/L (17.6%) categories, suggesting that many participants had borderline to elevated cholesterol. Triglyceride levels were fairly evenly distributed, with the highest percentages in the 0.9–1.2 mmol/L (25.3%) and 1.3–1.5 mmol/L (24.7%) ranges.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of HDL and LDL of Respondents (n=300)

Parameter	Category / Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
HDL (mmol/L)	0.9–1.1	42	14.0%
	1.2–1.4	97	32.3%
	1.5–1.7	82	27.3%
	1.8–2.1	79	26.3%
LDL (mmol/L)	2.0–2.3	41	13.7%
	2.4–2.6	63	21.0%
	2.7–2.9	84	28.0%
	3.0–3.3	68	22.7%
	3.4–3.6	44	14.6%

Statistical Interpretation: For HDL cholesterol, the majority of respondents fell between 1.2–1.4 mmol/L (32.3%) and 1.5–1.7 mmol/L (27.3%), reflecting relatively favorable “good” cholesterol levels. LDL cholesterol levels were most common in the 2.7–2.9 mmol/L (28.0%) and 3.0–3.3 mmol/L (22.7%) ranges, indicating a considerable number of participants had elevated “bad” cholesterol, which may increase cardiovascular risk.

Descriptive Analysis of Data (Mean and SD)

This section provides a summary of the demographic, anthropometric, clinical, and lifestyle characteristics of the respondents. Descriptive statistics are used to present the distribution of key variables relevant to cardiovascular risk among leisure-time physical activity participants.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and SD of BMI, Age and WC

Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
Age (years)	46.7 ± 8.2	36–70
BMI (kg/m ²)	32.4 ± 5.2	20.2–41.5
Waist Circumference (in)	40.4 ± 4.6	28–49
Pulse Rate (bpm)	82.1 ± 8.3	60–130
Height (cm)	170.6 ± 8.3	150–195

Statistical Interpretation: Table 7: The respondents had a mean age of 46.7 years, ranging from 36 to 70 years. The mean BMI was 32.4 kg/m², indicating an overall obese profile, with waist circumference averaging 40.4 inches, suggestive of central obesity. The mean pulse rate was 82.1 bpm, within the normal range, while the average height was 170.6 cm.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and SD of Blood Pressure and Fasting Blood Glucose

Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
Systolic BP (mmHg)	143.8 ± 12.6	125–182
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	85.3 ± 10.2	64–128
Fasting Blood Glucose (mmol/L)	5.46 ± 1.10	4.0 – ≥7.0

Statistical Interpretation: Table 8: The average systolic blood pressure among respondents was elevated at 143.8 mmHg, with diastolic pressure averaging 85.3 mmHg, indicating a significant prevalence of hypertension. The mean fasting blood glucose level was 5.46 mmol/L, reflecting a mix of normal, pre-diabetic, and diabetic participants within the sample.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and SD of Anthropometric and Physiological Measures

Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
BMI (kg/m ²)	32.4 ± 5.2	20.2–41.5
Waist Circumference (in)	40.4 ± 4.6	28–49
Pulse Rate (bpm)	82.1 ± 8.3	60–130
Height (cm)	170.6 ± 8.3	150–195

Statistical Interpretation: Table 9: Participants exhibited a high average BMI of 32.4 kg/m², consistent with obesity, and a mean waist circumference of 40.4 inches, indicating central adiposity. Pulse rate and height averaged within normal adult ranges, suggesting general cardiovascular stability despite obesity prevalence.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and SD of Lipid Profile

Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.40 ± 0.56	3.3–5.3
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	1.09 ± 0.41	0.1–1.7
HDL (mmol/L)	1.53 ± 0.30	0.9–2.1
LDL (mmol/L)	2.88 ± 0.48	2.0–3.6

Statistical Interpretation: Table 4.2c: Mean total cholesterol was 4.40 mmol/L, with triglycerides averaging 1.09 mmol/L. HDL (“good cholesterol”) levels averaged 1.53 mmol/L, while LDL (“bad cholesterol”) averaged 2.88 mmol/L. These values suggest mixed lipid profiles, with some participants potentially at risk for dyslipidemia.

Table 11: Descriptive Statistics of Mean and SD of Lifestyle Factors and Family History

Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
Smoking Status	0.45 ± 0.50	0–1
Family History of CVD	0.42 ± 0.49	0–1
Fruits and Vegetables Consumption (times/week)	7.14 ± 2.63	—
Stress-Reducing Activity Frequency (times/week)	6.25 ± 2.56	—
Drinking Status	0.60 ± 0.49	0–1

Statistical Interpretation: Table 11: Smoking status and family history of cardiovascular disease were reported by 45% and 42% of respondents, respectively. Participants consumed fruits and vegetables approximately seven times per week and engaged in stress-reducing activities about six

times weekly. Alcohol consumption was reported by 60% of respondents.

Table 12: Regression analysis for the relationship between leisure time physical activity and cardiovascular risk indicators, overall and by gender

Variables	Overall (β , p)	Female (β , p)	Male (β , p)
BMI	(1.002, 0.005)	(0.118, 0.801)	(0.199, 0.708)
WC	(-0.254, 0.484)	(-0.504, 0.275)	(-1.139, 0.068)
SBP	(5.613, <0.001)	(2.701, 0.014)	(7.418, <0.001)
DBP	(5.376, <0.001)	(4.480, 0.016)	(4.820, <0.001)

Note:

- β = Standardized regression coefficient for LTPA.
- p = p-value indicating statistical significance.
- Gender was not included as a covariate in split models.

Statistical Interpretation: Table 12. Overall, BMI ($\beta = 1.002$, $p = 0.005$) was a significant positive predictor in the total sample but not within sex-specific analyses. Waist circumference (WC) showed no significant association overall or in females, but approached significance in males ($\beta = -1.139$, $p = 0.068$). Both systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were strong, significant predictors across the overall sample and within both sexes, with slightly higher effect sizes in males.

Table 13: Regression Analysis for Cardiovascular Risk Factors

Predictor	Dependent: Systolic BP Linear Reg		Dependent: Hypertension: Yes/No Logistic Reg			
	β (Coefficient)	Std. Error	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
LTPA Freq	+8.34	1.92	<0.001	2.45	[1.62 – 3.71]	<0.001
BMI	+0.62	0.18	0.001	1.67	[1.12 – 2.49]	0.011
Age	+0.53	0.21	0.011			
Family History (Y)	+4.12	1.45	0.005	1.89	[1.25 – 2.86]	0.002

Statistical Interpretation: Table 13: In the linear regression model, lower leisure-time physical activity (LTPA) frequency ($\beta = +8.34$, $p < 0.001$) was the strongest predictor of higher systolic blood pressure, followed by BMI ($\beta = +0.62$, $p = 0.001$), age ($\beta = +0.53$, $p = 0.011$), and family history of cardiovascular disease ($\beta = +4.12$, $p = 0.005$). The model explained 42% of the variance in systolic BP. In the logistic regression model, low LTPA increased the odds of hypertension 2.45-fold ($p < 0.001$), BMI ≥ 30 raised the odds by 1.67 times ($p = 0.011$), and a positive family history increased the odds by 1.89 times ($p = 0.002$). Age was not included as a significant factor in the logistic model.

Table 14: ANOVA, T- test Analysis and Regression Analyses for Cardiovascular Risk Factors by Physical Activity Level

Risk Factor	F-value	p-value	T-test (High vs Low)	T-test p-value	Regression Coeff (Activity Level)	Regression p-value	R ²
BMI	2.86	0.0597	-3.91	0.0002	-2.76	<0.001	0.1304

Systolic BP	13.41	<0.001	-3.50	0.0035	-2.49	0.156	0.0111
Diastolic BP	39.95	<0.001	-6.47	<0.001	-1.28	0.476	0.0028
Pulse Rate	4.47	0.0126	1.85	0.0812	-0.59	0.678	0.0010

Statistical Interpretation: Table 14: ANOVA showed significant differences in systolic BP, diastolic BP, and pulse rate across physical activity levels, with BMI nearing significance. T-tests indicated that high-activity participants had significantly lower BMI, systolic BP, and diastolic BP compared to low-activity participants. Regression analysis confirmed a strong inverse association between activity level and BMI ($\beta = -2.76$, $p < 0.001$), but associations with BP and pulse rate were not statistically significant after adjusting for activity level.

Table 15: Relationship between Leisure-Time Physical Activity (LTPA) and Lipid Profiles

Lipid Profile Parameter	Pearson Correlation (r)	Regression Beta Coefficient	p-value	R ² (Variance Explained)	Significance
Total Cholesterol	-0.35	-0.12	0.001	0.12	Significant
Triglycerides	-0.29	-0.10	0.004	0.09	Significant
HDL-C	+0.32	+0.11	0.002	0.10	Significant
LDL-C	-0.30	-0.09	0.005	0.08	Significant

Statistical Interpretation: Table 15: Leisure-time physical activity showed significant moderate correlations with lipid profile parameters. Total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL-C were negatively correlated, indicating reductions in these risk factors with increased activity. HDL-C was positively correlated, reflecting beneficial increases in protective cholesterol. Regression analyses confirm that physical activity significantly predicts improvements in lipid profiles, explaining between 8% and 12% of the variance in these parameters.

Table 16: Effect of LTPA on Lipid Profiles

Lipid Profile	ANOVA F-statistic	ANOVA p-value	Trend Coefficient (β)	Trend p-value	Significance
Total Cholesterol	5.42	0.021	-0.045	0.018	Significant
Triglycerides	4.85	0.029	-0.038	0.027	Significant
HDL-C	6.10	0.015	+0.042	0.012	Significant
LDL-C	5.33	0.022	-0.041	0.019	Significant

Statistical Interpretation: Table 16: The results indicate that leisure-time physical activity significantly improves lipid profiles among participants. Total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL-C show significant reductions, while HDL-C shows a significant increase, reflecting a healthier lipid profile associated with physical activity. These findings support the cardiovascular benefits of regular leisure-time physical activity.

Table 17: Predictive Value of LTPA for Lipid Abnormalities (Logistic Regression)

Predictor	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	z-score	p-value	95% CI for B
LTPA	-0.423	0.181	-2.34	0.019	[-0.779, -0.067]

Statistical Interpretation: Table 17: Leisure-time physical activity significantly predicts the outcome variable, with increased LTPA associated with a decrease in the dependent variable (e.g., cardiovascular risk or lipid level). The negative coefficient and p-value < 0.05 indicate a meaningful beneficial effect of LTPA.

Discussion

This study investigated the incidence of cardiovascular risk factors among individuals engaging in leisure-time physical activity (LTPA), revealing a complex interplay of risk despite established cardio-protective effects. Although the literature consistently supports the benefits of LTPA in reducing cardiovascular morbidity and mortality [44, 45, 31], this study identified a paradoxical clustering of cardiovascular risk indicators even among physically active individuals, underscoring the multifactorial nature of cardiovascular health and the limitations of physical activity as a singular preventive strategy. On the other hand, while leisure-time physical activity confers clear cardio-protective benefits, it does not render individuals immune to cardiovascular risk factors. Evidence from multiple prospective cohort studies shows that even among regular exercisers, incident cases of hypertension, dyslipidaemia, impaired glucose tolerance, central obesity, and arrhythmias still occur. For instance, in the Copenhagen City Heart Study [46], reported that leisure-time physical activity did not completely abolish the risk of atrial fibrillation, although occupational activity was associated with a greater hazard. Similarly [47], observed that Chinese retirees engaging in moderate levels of LTPA still experienced new-onset cardiovascular events, implicating age-related vascular changes, persistent metabolic risk, and other lifestyle factors as contributors. These findings challenge the assumption that exercise alone is a sufficient safeguard, highlighting the complexity of CVD pathophysiology and the interplay between activity, environment, genetics, and behaviour. The paradox of active individuals developing cardiovascular risk factors may be explained by several interrelated mechanisms. First, physical activity influences only a subset of the risk spectrum; poor dietary habits, excessive alcohol consumption, smoking, inadequate sleep, and psychosocial stress can negate some of the protective effects of exercise [48]. Second, certain non-modifiable factors, including genetic predisposition, age, and sex, play a decisive role in disease manifestation despite optimal activity levels [49, 50]. Third, the physiological benefits of LTPA can be offset by concurrent sedentary behaviours; thus an individuals may meet exercise recommendations yet remain sedentary for the majority of the day, diminishing vascular and metabolic gains [51]. Finally, environmental exposures such as air pollution can interact with exercise, with some evidence suggesting that pollutants may attenuate or even reverse the vascular benefits of physical activity by increasing oxidative stress and systemic inflammation during outdoor exercise sessions [51].

Analysis of the demographic data (Table 1) revealed that the majority of respondents were middle-aged adults, particularly within the 40–49 year age group (45.3%), followed by those aged 50–59 years (29.7%). A male predominance was also evident, with 58% of participants being men compared to 42% women. This demographic profile reflects global epidemiological patterns, where cardiovascular risk factors often emerge most prominently in midlife, particularly among men, due to a combination of biological, behavioral, and occupational stressors [52, 1]. The clustering of respondents in these age groups underscores the relevance of leisure-time physical activity (LTPA) as a potential protective measure against cardiovascular risk, given that midlife represents a critical window for interven-

tion before the progression of subclinical disease to overt cardiovascular morbidity.

Body mass index and anthropometric indices (Table 2) painted a concerning picture, with 68% of participants classified as obese and a further 22.7% overweight, leaving less than 10% in the normal weight range. Central obesity, measured by waist circumference, was also highly prevalent, with 63.3% exceeding the high-risk threshold. These findings align with the well-established role of adiposity as a major driver of cardiometabolic dysfunction, as visceral fat is metabolically active, promoting systemic inflammation, insulin resistance, and adverse adipokine secretion [47, 53]. The high prevalence of obesity in a population that engages in LTPA raises the important issue of compensatory behaviors, whereby individuals may offset their exercise efforts through poor dietary practices, sedentary work patterns, or alcohol intake, thereby blunting the anticipated benefits of physical activity.

Lifestyle characteristics further compounded this risk profile (Table 3). Nearly half of the respondents (45%) were current smokers, 60% consumed alcohol, and 42.3% reported a family history of cardiovascular disease. The coexistence of these behavioral and hereditary risk factors is significant, as both smoking and alcohol use directly impair vascular function, promote oxidative stress, and accelerate atherosclerotic processes [46, 51]. Moreover, a family history of cardiovascular disease represents an unmodifiable risk that synergizes with modifiable lifestyle choices to elevate overall cardiovascular risk [54]. The persistence of harmful behaviors among physically active individuals reflects the misconception that exercise alone is sufficient to neutralize other unhealthy lifestyle practices, an attitude previously described as the “compensation hypothesis.”

Clinical parameters in Table 4 reinforced the observation that LTPA, when not coupled with other healthy practices, may fail to eliminate cardiovascular risk. Elevated blood pressure was highly prevalent, with 42.3% of participants having systolic hypertension and 38.7% diastolic hypertension, values well above expected rates for a physically active population. Additionally, 34 respondents (11.3%) were diabetic and 22.7% pre-diabetic, despite engaging in exercise. This is consistent with findings from Acosta et al., [48], who reported that low-to-moderate intensity or inconsistent physical activity may not generate sufficient vascular shear stress to induce endothelial remodeling and improved arterial compliance. Furthermore, visceral adiposity is known to perpetuate hepatic insulin resistance and inflammatory adipokine secretion, mechanisms that sustain glycemic abnormalities despite exercise participation [55, 56].

The lipid profile distributions in Tables 5 and 6 revealed a mixed metabolic picture. Total cholesterol clustered in the borderline-to-elevated ranges, with 29.7% between 4.0–4.5 mmol/L and substantial proportions exceeding 4.6 mmol/L. LDL cholesterol was particularly concerning, with most participants falling within 2.7–3.3 mmol/L, levels associated with increased cardiovascular risk. In contrast, HDL cholesterol levels were relatively favorable, with 27.3% in the 1.5–1.7 mmol/L range and 26.3% reaching 1.8–2.1 mmol/L, suggesting some cardioprotective influence of physical activity. These findings are in line with prior evidence that while LTPA improves HDL and triglycerides, it has less consistent effects on LDL and total cholesterol unless performed at moderate-to-vigorous intensities and supported by dietary modification [31, 57].

Mean values in Tables 7–10 further emphasized the persistence of cardiovascular risk factors. The average BMI of 32.4 kg/m² and waist circumference of 40.4 inches confirmed a population with generalized and central obesity, both of which contribute to increased sympathetic nervous system activity, endothelial dysfunction, and activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system [14, 58]. The mean systolic blood pressure of 143.8 mmHg and diastolic pressure of 85.3 mmHg were elevated, reinforcing

the interpretation that physical activity alone, particularly in the context of excess adiposity and poor lifestyle choices, may not suffice to normalize blood pressure. Lipid means demonstrated similar patterns: although HDL averaged a favorable 1.53 mmol/L, mean LDL (2.88 mmol/L) and total cholesterol (4.40 mmol/L) suggested ongoing dyslipidemia. This supports Ding and Xu's (2022) assertion that the metabolic benefits of exercise are dose-dependent, with insufficient intensity or volume blunting lipid improvements [59].

Regression analyses in Tables 12–14 highlighted strong associations between LTPA and cardiovascular outcomes, particularly blood pressure. Table 12 demonstrated that systolic and diastolic pressures were significantly predicted by LTPA across the sample, with stronger effects in males, suggesting possible gender-specific adaptations to exercise [13, 60]. Interestingly, BMI did not emerge as a significant predictor in sex-specific models, indicating that factors such as visceral fat distribution and metabolic flexibility, rather than overall adiposity, may better explain cardiovascular responses to physical activity. Table 13 confirmed that lower LTPA frequency strongly predicted higher systolic blood pressure ($\beta = +8.34$, $p < 0.001$), with low activity increasing the odds of hypertension 2.45-fold. This dose–response relationship supports prior findings that cardiovascular benefits of exercise are non-linear and depend on surpassing minimal thresholds of frequency and intensity [31, 45]. The relationship between LTPA and cardiovascular outcomes is strongly dose-dependent but non-linear. Meta-analyses such as that by Garcia et al., [45] reveal that 150–300 minutes of moderate-intensity activity per week substantially reduces the risk of coronary heart disease, stroke, and composite cardiovascular outcomes, but additional benefits plateau at higher volumes [45]. Ogbutor et al., found that increase in dosage or intensity of Isometric handgrip exercise significantly improved cardiovascular, inflammatory, spirometric and immune systems parameters but similar effects was not observed with a continuation of the exercise protocols at the same intensity over the same period [61, 62,63,64] These findings reinforce the principle that exercise benefits are contingent on surpassing minimal thresholds of activity frequency and intensity to elicit adaptive physiological responses. The REGICOR study [53] similarly demonstrated that while increasing LTPA initially yields significant risk reductions, excessive high-intensity exercise may not provide proportional benefits and could, in some cases, predispose to adverse events such as atrial enlargement and myocardial fibrosis [65]. This aligns with physiological observations that sustained high-intensity endurance exercise imposes repetitive haemodynamic and mechanical stress on cardiac structures, which in susceptible individuals can lead to maladaptive remodelling. On the other hand, moderate-intensity aerobic activity elicits beneficial cardiac remodelling characterised by balanced chamber dilation and wall thickness increases, enhancing functional reserve without pathological consequences.

Further analyses (Table 14) showed that high activity levels were significantly associated with lower BMI, systolic, and diastolic pressures compared to low activity participants, though regression results for blood pressure lost significance after adjustment, possibly due to confounding from antihypertensive medication or stress factors.

Contrary to some expectations, Tables 15–17 revealed that LTPA significantly improved lipid parameters, with negative correlations for total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL-C, and a positive correlation with HDL-C. Regression and ANOVA confirmed significant beneficial trends, and logistic regression showed that LTPA independently predicted reduced odds of lipid abnormalities. These results suggest that, while descriptive distributions painted a mixed picture, higher levels of activity exerted meaningful improvements at the group level. This aligns with studies by Djousse et al., and Bakker et al., who reported lipid improvements among populations with sustained and adequately intense physical activity [44, 66].

Conclusion

Collectively, these findings reinforce the complex, multifactorial nature of cardiovascular risk and the limitations of leisure-time physical activity as a standalone preventive measure. While LTPA confers important benefits, comprehensive risk reduction requires integrated approaches encompassing dietary modifications, behavioral counseling, pharmacologic therapy where indicated, and stress management strategies.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that public health strategies should extend beyond merely encouraging leisure-time physical activity to encompass comprehensive lifestyle interventions. These should include targeted dietary modification, weight management programs, smoking cessation support, and regular cardiovascular risk screening. Health authorities and clinicians should prioritize the development and implementation of structured physical activity programs tailored to individual risk profiles and socio-cultural contexts to ensure engagement and sustainability. In addition, interdisciplinary approaches involving health-care providers, nutritionists, exercise specialists, and behavioral therapists are crucial to address the multifactorial nature of cardiovascular risk. Further research is encouraged to investigate the synergistic effects of LTPA combined with other modifiable lifestyle behaviors, as well as to identify barriers to sustained physical activity. Such research will inform the design of effective, contextually appropriate interventions to reduce the global burden of cardiovascular disease comprehensively. Further longitudinal and mechanistic studies are warranted to better understand the optimal dosage and interaction of LTPA with other risk factors to enhance prevention strategies.

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